

ECOLOGY AS A MAIN FACTOR OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF BELARUS

ЭКОЛОГИЯ КАК ГЛАВНЫЙ ФАКТОР ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ БЕЛАРУСИ

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Аннотация. В данной статье затрагивается тема зеленой экономики, которая является центральным аспектом устойчивого экономического развития. Цель статьи заключается в рассмотрении экологии как основного фактора, влияющего на развитие страны. Прослежены причины появления экологических проблем в Беларуси и описаны результаты осуществления деятельности зеленой экономики.

Annotation. This article deals with the topic of green economy, which is a central aspect of sustainable economic development. The aim of the article is to consider ecology as the main factor influencing the development of the country. The causes of environmental problems in Belarus are traced and the results of the implementation of green economy are described.

Ключевые слова: зеленая экономика, устойчивое развитие, проблемы окружающей среды, переход к зеленой экономике, экономическое развитие.

Keywords: green economy, sustainable development, environmental problems, transitioning to a green economy, economic development.

Nowadays ecology is heavily related with economic, political, social aspects. The use of machine fuel, large-scale deforestation, industrial production and the disasters of nuclear power plants have led to climate change. As a result, environmental disasters appear: melting of the Arctic ice, reduction of biodiversity, climate warming, the occurrence of the greenhouse effect, ozone holes, acid rain, etc. All this cannot but affect the economies of individual countries and the global economy as a whole.

In order to improve the economic situation and protect the population, a number of agreements and protocols were signed, certain organizations were created. The main aim was to search and improve international standards and recommendations for state economic and environmental policy. A number of countries are trying to achieve sustainable economic development.

The definition of sustainable development was introduced by the English economist Thomas Robert Malthus in the 18th century. He formulated the thought: the population is increasing faster than the growth of food production and resources. In the future, this leads to catastrophes like hunger, poverty and wars. In 1972, the United Nations was established in order to solve environmental issues on a global scale. In 2015 the UN General Assembly developed 17 interrelated goals for the achievement of a better and more sustainable future in economic, environmental and social aspects [3].

To achieve sustainable development of any country it is necessary to develop a combination of measures aimed at meeting current human needs with maintaining the comfort environment for future generations to meet their own needs. Ecological balance is one of the factors of sustainable development.

As it has been mentioned earlier, the world's natural resources are being destroyed by the present economic system. The costs associated with climate change and loss of biodiversity are increasing every year and can amount up to a quarter of the world's gross national product by 2050 [2]. A new economic development called Green Economy should solve this problem. To achieve a harmony between economy and environment, Green Economy should concentrate on the increase of society well-being. Green future markets are characterized by energy efficiency, environmentally friendly energy production, sustainable resource management and recycling. The transitioning to a green economy is quite challenging, but it improves operational efficiency by optimizing resource usage, embracing renewable energy, reducing waste.

The tendency of transitioning to green economy is gaining popularity among developed and developing countries. Belarus isn't exception. Today Belarus is moving towards sustainable development.

The green economy is the highest priority in Belarus. The national strategy for sustainable development of the Republic of Belarus highlights 2 stages. The goal of the first stage (2016-2020) was the transition to a green economy with the use of high-tech industries, which are necessary to improve the competitiveness of our economy and upgrade the quality of everyday life of the population.

The design of the Program of Socio-Economic Development of the Republic of Belarus for 2021 to 2025 and the National Strategy for Sustainable Development of the Republic of Belarus up to 2035 are the normative legal acts of the second stage in the national strategy for the sustainable development of the Republic of Belarus. In 2021, some areas that contribute to the development of a green economy were identified. They are the development of eco-tourism, the formation of energy-efficient cities, the development of electric transport and urban mobility. These areas will not only improve the quality of population's life, but also improve the economy and ecology of the country. The following items were also included in this list: the development of organic production, adaptation to climate change, the conservation of biological and landscape diversity. It's necessary to understand that without the scientific support it is impossible to make the transition towards a green economy [2].

Belarusian environmental problems include radioactive contamination of the territory, atmospheric air pollution, surface and groundwater pollution, soil pollution and degradation, generation and accumulation of waste.

The most vital problem connected with the occupied area is the problem of radioactive contamination of the Belarusian territory. According to the radiation monitoring data of the Department of Hydrometeorology, at the beginning of 2008, the area of contamination with cesium-137 amounted to 19.8% of the country's territory. 1308.6 thousand people were living within the territory with radioactive contamination. 20.8% of the lands of the State Forest Fund and 13.5% of agricultural lands are exposed to radioactive contamination [4]. This leads to an equally urgent problem - land use. Lands are the main natural resources for the development of Belarus. The accident at the Chernobyl nuclear power plant still affects the economy of Belarus. The accident limited not only the country's natural resource potential, but also required large expenditures to reduce radiation hazards.

The State Program adopted in the Republic of Belarus assumes some measures to overcome the consequences of the Chernobyl disaster. It includes radiation monitoring of agricultural and forest products, food and water, rehabilitation of contaminated areas and maintenance of exclusion

and resettlement zones, the decontamination of socially significant facilities, the burial of radioactive waste.

Land reclamation is another problem that requires special attention from the state. Large-scale drainage and reclamation works have caused a violation of the ecological balance of natural systems. Swamps and wetlands make up 40% of the territory of Belarus, therefore, solving the problems of land reclamation are necessary for economic development. The main aim is to preserve the established reclamation complex, reduce the costs assigned for the maintenance and development of reclaimed lands. For the proper functioning of the land reclamation system, it is necessary to provide additional funding for the modernization of equipment, the search for new ways to achieve the goals set.

Another environmental problem of the Republic of Belarus is connected with the waste accumulation and disposal. Every year, approximately 24 million tons of industrial waste are produced on the territory of Belarus, 240 thousand tons of which are toxic. All garbage is taken to landfills with a total area of 890 hectares, and 60% of this territory is already occupied. These landfills occupy a significant part of the land resources. Landfills contribute to an increase in environmental pollution. There are 80 sorting stations operating in the country, which have reduced the volume of solid waste exported to landfill by 30%. Most of the municipal waste sorting points are part of the housing and communal services system. It is necessary to learn how to extract as much benefit and profit from waste as possible [5].

A system of continuous environmental education has been established in Belarus. Environmental lessons are included in the education programs of kindergartens and schools. In 2022, 400 Belarusian schools have received the status of "green": waste paper, batteries and other waste are being collected. This is how children spread environmental knowledge, which stimulates the adult population to eco-friendly consumption [1].

In conclusion, ecology plays a crucial role in the economic development of Belarus. The country's natural resources and environment are key assets that contribute to its overall prosperity. Belarus is known for its rich biodiversity, vast forests and numerous rivers and lakes, which provide important ecosystem services that support various industries and sectors of the economy.

The sustainable management of both natural resources and protection of the environment are top priorities for Belarus as they directly impact the country's economic growth and well-being. By investing in eco-friendly technologies, promoting renewable energy sources and implementing strict environmental regulations Belarus aims to balance economic development with environmental conservation.

One of the vital components driving economic development in Belarus is the country's commitment to green initiatives and sustainable practices. By prioritizing ecology and environmental protection, Belarus attracts investments from environmentally conscious businesses and promotes a positive image on the international stage. Additionally, eco-tourism has been growing in popularity in Belarus, as visitors are drawn to the country's pristine nature reserves and protected areas.

Furthermore, a healthy environment contributes to the well-being of Belarusian citizens, as clean air, water, and soil are essential for public health and quality of life. By preserving its natural resources and reducing pollution levels, Belarus ensures a sustainable future for its population and future generations.

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